

TABLE 1

System	$E_{1/2}$ in volt vs S.C.E. (at 25°)	αn (at 25°)	$id/h_{1/2}$ ($\mu\text{amp cm}^{-1/2}$)	Activation Energy of Diffusion [Kcal]	Diffusion Current Constant (at 25°)	Diffusion Coefficient (at 25°) $\times 10^5$
Ethanolamine (1.0 M) NaOH (0.1 M)						
No ligand	-0.489	0.9456	0.570	3.76	2.52	1.933
Monoethanolamine	-0.489	0.8628	0.489	3.80	2.16	1.704
Diethanolamine	-0.499	0.8756	0.422	5.54	1.96	1.347
N-methyl diethanolamine	-0.511	0.9234	0.366	5.66	1.63	0.813
Triethanolamine	-0.519	0.9234	0.340	7.38	1.50	0.721

It appears from the half-wave potential values that MEA does not form any complex with Tl(I) whereas appreciable complex formation takes place with DEA, MDEA and TEA. With a view to study the relative complexing ability of different ethanolamines, polarograms were recorded with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tl(I), 0.1M NaOH and varying concentrations of the ligands. It has been observed that except with MEA, both the half-wave potentials and the diffusion currents progressively decreased with the increase of ligand concentration. In case of MEA, only the diffusion current decreased slightly with increasing ligand concentration. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ for DEA and MDEA systems were marginal. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs logarithm of TEA concentrations was linear which indicated the presence of a single complex species in solution.

For a sufficiently weak complex of the type ML_x , the diffusion current (i_d) for the reduction of M can be related with the ligand concentration (C_L) by the following expression,

$$i_d^{-1} = K^{-1} \cdot a^{-1} + k(K \cdot a)^{-1} C_L^x$$

where,

K = diffusion current per unit concentration of the depolarizer.

k = stability constant of the complex.

C_L = total ligand concentration.

a = concentration of M.

x = number of ligands per metal ion.

The plot of $1/i_d$ vs concentration of ethanolamines (C_L) for 1.0 mM Tl (I) polarographed under identical

condition is shown in the figure. The virtually horizontal curve for MEA-system indicates that no complex formation takes place. The initial slight rise may be attributed to the slight change of the supporting electrolyte due to the change of MEA concentration and the effect is imperceptible at higher ligand concentrations. The linear curves with gradually increasing slopes for the DEA, MDEA and TEA systems show that ML type complexes having $x=1$ are formed in solution. The stability order is $TEA > MDEA > DEA$, the slopes being proportional to the stability constants. The results are in agreement with the shifts of the $E_{1/2}$ values of Tl (I) in presence of these ligands.

References

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Mercury(II) Complexes with Substituted Thiourea

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SEVERAL complexes of zinc (II), cadmium (II) and mercury (II) with thiourea have been reported¹⁻³ earlier. Since comparatively less number of mercury (II) complexes are known, it was thought worthwhile to study the complexes of mercury(II) with some substituted thiourea and the present investigation reports seven compounds of mercury (II) having the composition $[Hg L Cl_2]$, where L is N-methyl, N,N'-diethyl, N-allyl, o-tolyl, p-tolyl, N-phenyl and N,N'-diphenyl thiourea.

Experimental :

Aqueous solution of mercury (II) chloride was reacted with ethanolic solution of different substituted thiourea in 1:2 ratio. Some of the halide complexes appear immediately after vigorous shaking. A few of the complexes were formed after keeping the mixture standing for some hours. The precipitated compounds are suction filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. The composition of the complexes are determined by estimating metal, halogen and sulfur by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 0.001M acetone solution using a Toshniwal

